

«ÚZLIKSIZ BILIMLENDIRIW SISTEMASÍDA ARALÍQTAN OQÍTÍWDÍN INTEGRACIYASÍ» atamasındaǵı IV Xalıqaralıq ilimiy-teoriyalıq konferenciya

THE SYSTEM ORGANIZATION OF INTEGRATIVE MEDICAL SCIENCES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Annotation. *The activity of the higher education system is aimed at training qualified specialists and experts, based on the requirements in the field of professional activity of highly qualified specialists, ensuring active use of integrative sciences to find solutions to situations that arise in the professional process.*

Keywords: *higher education system, specialist, integration, science, medicine, innovative technologies, interest, professional skills, physical education, development, growth, movement.*

In universities, expanding students' medical knowledge and literacy is one of the most pressing issues. A healthy society empowers the nation. While our youth's medical literacy is gradually increasing, some students and educators fail to recognize the need for specialized knowledge in the medical field. It is essential for educators to have the necessary skills to recognize the causes of diseases among students, their prevention, consequences, and to provide timely medical assistance when needed, whether through telemedicine or in stationary settings, using various effective technologies based on pedagogical methods, means and forms.

In accordance with the National Program approved by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. M. Mirziyoyev for the Development of Public Education for 2022-2026 (May 7, 2022), it is crucial to enhance the scientific-research and professional competencies of students in the higher education system by conducting classes in a competent manner, following the Decree of our President dated May 5, 2022 [1]. It is also of great importance to improve the activities of the Scientific-Practical Center of the Republican Sports Medicine under the supervision of the Uzbekistan National Olympic Committee to provide skilled medical personnel for sports teams, to equip athletes with necessary innovative equipment for their activities, and to enhance the medical knowledge of physical education

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teachers through physical training, which is essential for the development of medical sciences.

Medical science serves the field of human health preservation and enhancement, encompassing the scientific and practical activities of individuals involved in preventing, diagnosing, and treating diseases [2].

In essence, medicine is a specific form of human knowledge. It is more practical than speculative. The method of development of medical sciences is also practical: medicine unites medical knowledge, principles, and interpretations to organize them for practical purposes. Moreover, adapting essential medical concepts to medicine gives it a unique “art”. Having medical knowledge enables individuals to understand the causes and consequences of diseases, which leads to constant actions for disease prevention (creating a healthy lifestyle, maintaining hygiene, avoiding harmful habits). This, in turn, promotes longevity [3].

Various unforeseen circumstances may arise in life, especially among physical education teachers, sports trainers, and healthcare professionals, where serious diseases may be encountered. For instance, encountering a patient with respiratory distress, a cardiac event, or an injured athlete might necessitate immediate medical assistance. Not being equipped with medical knowledge in such situations, or fearing to provide assistance, may lead to adverse outcomes for patients.

Through innovative technologies and pedagogical interactive methods, young professionals engaged in education, particularly those involved in medical sciences, can effectively provide initial assistance without losing composure in critical situations.

The term “integration” in the Uzbek National Encyclopedia is derived from the Latin word “integratio”, which means completion or fulfillment, and from the word “integer”, which signifies entirety. It is defined as follows:

1. Integration refers to a concept that illustrates the interconnectedness of various parts and functions within a system or organism, as well as the processes leading to such a state.
2. It involves the convergence and mutual relationship of disciplines and subjects through differentiation.
3. Integration is also utilized in contexts such as enhancing and unifying the economies of two or more states.

Integration is a significant principle in modernizing the educational process and holds a crucial place in educational development. In pedagogical terms,

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integration is used to deepen and enhance interdisciplinary knowledge (integrative knowledge) and to promote their development.

Several scholars from Saint Petersburg (Leningrad) University and the Institute of Physical Education have actively contributed to the current integration of scientific schools. Researchers such as I. M. Sechenov, N. E. Vedensky, A. A. Ukhtomsky, M. I. Vinogradov, E. K. Zhukov, I. P. Pavlov, A. S. Batuev, V. A. Doroshenko, V. G. Komenskaya, P. F. Lesgaft, A. A. Krasuya, A. T. Stump, E. A. Ktikova, E. G. Ktelnikova, I. M. Koryakovskiy, D. A. Semenov, V. A. Petrov, I. P. Volkov, Yu. A. Gagin, I. M. Kozlov, G. P. Ivanova have made significant contributions to research in various fields.

The integration of various sciences, both theoretical and empirical, results in the emergence of integration. One of the positive aspects of integration is that successful scientific research may emerge as a result of the consolidation of scientific knowledge, relations, and best practices across different fields. This approach can lead to the development of new knowledge in fields such as medicine, sports, and pedagogy through their integration.

Integration plays a vital role in enhancing medical knowledge among students in the higher education system, thereby increasing their motivation towards medical sciences. The engagement of physical education teachers in developing medical knowledge is essential, and curiosity is the key to fostering it. "Curiosity is the inherent tendency toward exploration and inquisitiveness which drives motivational processes, resulting in outcomes such as perseverance, cognitive growth, and the enhancement of curiosity itself" [4]. Curiosity serves as a motivating factor in achieving goals and is essential for task performance and the acquisition of knowledge.

In conclusion, the integration of educational systems aims to produce specialized and effective professionals, and the proper utilization of integrated knowledge and theoretical understanding contributes to the formation of professional competencies.

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«ÚZLIKSIZ BILIMLENDIRIW SISTEMASÍDA ARALÍQTAN OQÍTÍWDÍN INTEGRACIYASÍ»

atamasındaǵı IV Xalıqaralıq ilimiy-teoriyalıq konferenciya

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